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Semantic field “pagan – heretic” in the perspective of the Byzantines and the Westerners in the Early Middle Ages with reference to the Slavs and the Balkans

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Paganism as such was often considered by the Early Medieval Christian missionaries only as an erroneous approach/interpretation of Christian religion, which should be “corrected”, and finally transformed into Christianity. The final aim of this formational and transformational process executed by Christian missionaries was clear – baptism into the Christian rite. However, these processes did not flow so soundly, and the Latin chronicles very frequently describe that, “*Slavi denuo relapsi sunt ad paganismum*”, which became almost a *topos* in medieval chronicles providing accounts on the Slavs.

The aim of this paper is to demonstrate, on the chosen case-studies, the similar *topoi* in the representation of notions related to the semantic fields of heresy in paganism in the mid-9th century texts, which are in some way interrelated to the accounts on the Slavic populations. The topics discussed here include: the accounts of Photius and Pope Nicholas I on the baptism of the Bulgarians; Photius’s narrative on the Russians and pagans; the account of the rebellion of Thomas the Slav.

Photius on the Filioque in the 860’s

Throughout the 9th century, diverse types of encounters between Byzantium, Francia and Rome occurred. The Christian East and West came in contact with adherents to paganism, as well as

to other belief systems, on many occasions at this time, and during the missionary endeavors in the first place¹.

During the 9th century, the representatives of Byzantine ecclesiastical and ruling circles came on many occasions into contact with the Latin West – with the Pope, as well as with the Frankish Emperors². Predominant place in those more direct or indirect contacts occupies the correspondence during the Patriarchates of Ignatius (847-858; 867-877) and Photius (858-867; 877-886), apart from other appeals made to Rome during this period³. Pope Nicholas I (858-867) wrote a letter to Hincmar of Reims, asking him to organize a generalized counterstatement and schedule a synod in the West, as a response to the Greek attack on the Latin churches, occurred during the Latin missionary activities in Bulgaria⁴ and the re-emergence of the *Filioque* controversy⁵. This disruption in the relations between East and West did not relate to ecclesiastical matters only. It also propelled a sense of generalized negative picture the Greeks came to play in the Occidental mind⁶.

The *Filioque* controversy between East and West⁷ had its 9th-century peak during the events related to the Frankish and Byzantine missionary activities in Bulgaria in 866⁸. The accusations

¹ The literature delving with Christian missions in the Early Middle Ages is too exhaustive, so I shall cite only some: Jonathan Shepard, “Byzantine relations with the outside world in the ninth century: and introduction”, in *Byzantium in the 9th Century: Dead or Alive? Papers from the Thirtieth Spring Symposium of Byzantine Studies. Birmingham, March 1996*, ed. by Leslie Brubaker (Aldershot: Ashgate, 1998), 167-180; Id., “Spreading the Word: Byzantine Missions”, in *The Oxford History of Byzantium*, ed. by Cyril Mango (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2002), 230-247; Id., “Orthodoxy and Northern Peoples: Goods, Gods and Guidelines”, in *A Companion to Byzantium*, ed. Liz James (Oxford: Blackwell Publishing, 2010), 171-186; Ian Wood, “Christians and pagans in ninth-century Scandinavia”, in *The Christianization of Scandinavia*, ed. by Peter Sawyer, Brigit Sawyer and Ian Wood (Alingsås: Viktoria Bokforlag, 1987), 36-67.

² On main trends in Byzantine ecclesiastical policy in the 9th century, see: Предраг Коматина, *Црквена политика Византије од краја иконоборства до смрти цара Василија I* (Београд: Византолошки Институт САНУ, 2014).

³ cf. Francis Dvornik, *The Photian Schism. History and Legend* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1970²), 19-20; on the relation between Pope Nicholas and Boris, see: Paul Kershaw, *Peaceful Kings. Peace, Power, and The Early Medieval Political Imagination* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2011), 234-240.

⁴ Dvornik, *The Photian Schism*, 91-131.

⁵ Cf. Henry Chadwick, *East and West: The Making of a Rift in the Church. From Apostolic Times until the Council of Florence* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2003), 160.

⁶ Chadwick, *East and West*, 163.

⁷ Cf. Φωτίου Επιστολαί, ed. I. Βαλεττα (Photius, *Epistolae*, ed. by Ioannos Valetta, London: David Nutt, 1864), Ep. 6.

⁸ Dvornik, *The Photian Schism*, 122; Despina Stratoudaki White, *Patriarch Photios of Constantinople: His Life, Scholarly Contributions, and Correspondence Together with a Translation of Fifty-two of His Letters* (Brookline-MA: Holy Cross Orthodox Press, 1981), 32; Photius, *De Spiritus S. mystagogia*, ed. by Joseph Hergenröther,

followed on behalf of the Byzantines, according to which the *Filioque*, introduced by the Latin bishops in Bulgaria, was similar to the older heresies, as well as to the tales of Greek mythology. The work of the Latin missionaries was consequently condemned by a local synod in Constantinople, held in 867⁹. The Council asked the innovations brought in by the Latin missionaries to be extirpated. Nicholas I got excommunicated by the Council. On this problematic, Photius directed a letter to the Oriental Patriarchs¹⁰, in which he condemns the liturgical practices introduced by the Latin missionaries in Bulgaria – which was officially expressed upon a Council of Constantinople, held in 867¹¹. It was upon this Council that the Pope Nicholas I got excommunicated¹².

In his Encyclical letter to the Patriarch of the East, Photius mainly focuses on condemning the “false doctrines” imposed on the Bulgarian people by the Frankish missionaries in Bulgaria¹³, whom he considered as impious men – ἄνδρες δυσσεβεῖς¹⁴.

The question on the procession of the Holy Spirit was mentioned in the Scriptures and continued to be present ever since in the writings of the holy fathers. Nevertheless, the disputes it induced

(Regensburg, 1857), 14, 15, 36, 37 109; Photius’s *Encyclical Letter to the Oriental Patriarchs* (Ep. 4), ed. Valetta, 165-181; Photius, *Encyclica Epistola*, ed. Migne, 721-741; Chadwick, *East and West*, 158-163.

⁹ Chadwick, *East and West*, 158-161; cf. Stratoudaki White, *Patriarch Photios*, 32-34.

¹⁰Photius’s letter to the Oriental Patriarchs: “Encyclica ad sedes orientales”, in *Photii Patriarchae Constantinopolitani Epistulae et Amphilochia*, vol. 1, ed. by Vasileios Laourda and Leendert G. Westernik (Leipzig: Teubner, 1983), 39-53; Photius, “Encyclica Epistola ad Archiepiscopales Thronos per Orientem obtinentes”, in *Patrologiae Cursus Completus, Series Graeca, Epistolarum Libri Tres*, ed. by Jean-Paul Migne (Paris: Imprimerie Catholique: 1857-1866), 102: 585-1000, here *Epistolarum liber I*, 721-741; cf. Tia M. Kolbaba, *Inventing Latin Heretics. Byzantines and the Filioque in the Ninth Century* (Kalamazoo-MI: Western Michigan University Press, 2008).

¹¹ On the summary on the particularities of the Latin liturgy which provoked the condemnation, cf. Cyril Mango, *The Homilies of Photius, Patriarch of Constantinople* (Harvard: Harvard University Press 1958), 300; Photius, *Encyclical Letter*, ed. Valetta, Ep. 4, 165-181; *Ibid.*, ed. Migne, 721-741.

¹² *Sacrorum Conciliorum nova et amplissima collectio*, edited by Giovanni-Domenico Mansi (Florenze/Venezia, 1759-1798), XVI, 174C, 405C; Nicetas David Paphlago, “Vita Archiepiscopi Ignatii Constantinopolitani sive Certamen”, in: *Patrologiae Cursus Completus, Series Graeca*, ed. by Jean-Paul Migne, 105: 487-574 (Paris: Imprimerie Catholique, 1857-1866), 541.

¹³ Photius, *Encyclical letter*, ed. Valetta, 168.

¹⁴ Photius’s *Encyclical letter*, ed. Valetta, 168.

were strongly related to the Christological issues dating from the dawn of the officialization of the Christian creed¹⁵. The *Filioque* controversy re-emerged again in the 9th-century¹⁶.

During his second exile, Photius composed a lengthy treatise entitled “The Mystagogia of The Holy Spirit” in which he exposed his view of the doctrinal matter and the position of the Eastern Church on the *Filioque* controversy. Even this dispute, according to Photius, could be placed in the line of older heresies, since he esteemed it comparable to the heresies of Sabellius and Macedonius¹⁷.

In his *De Spiritu Sancti Mystagogia*, Photius condemns the *Filioque* doctrine of the Latins: by adding that the Holy Spirit proceeds from the Son also, they made it a polytheistic dogma, which is, therefore, also atheistic; it falls in the genre of impious tales, and represents a pagan superstition under the guise of Christianity. Namely, by doing so, they support the existence of the two divine principles, instead of one only, and that is why Photius brings it into connection with polytheism: ...τὸ τῆς πολυθείας ἄθεον...ἐν προσχῆματι χριστιανισμοῦ ἢ δεισιδαιμονία τῆς Ἑλληνικῆς πλάνης...¹⁸

It was apparently in one of Photius’s letters that we encounter one of the first accounts on the differences between the Eastern and Western churches¹⁹.

¹⁵ The summarized analysis containing the most relevant information on the *Filioque* controversy in the Middle Ages is proposed by Siecienski, *The Filioque*; Cf. Ștefăniță Barbu, “Language, Philosophy and Politics in the Development of the Filioque Clause” in *Theologia Orthodoxa* 2010 (1): 257–271; Chadwick, *East and West*, 93; On Maximus the Confessor and the *Filioque* controversy, see: George Berthold, “Maximus the Confessor and the Filioque”, in *Studia Patristica* 18/1 (1985): 113–117.

¹⁶ On earlier doctrinal tendencies and conflicts, which nonetheless influence the course of events in the 9th century as well, see: John Meyendorff, *Imperial Unity and Christian Divisions: The Church 450-680 A.D.* (Crestwood: St. Vladimir’s Press, 1989); Andrew J. Ekonomou, *Byzantine Rome and the Greek Popes: Eastern influences on Rome and the papacy from Gregory the Great to Zacharias, A.D. 590-752* (Lanham-MD: Lexington Books, 2007); Edward A. Siecienski, *The Filioque: History of a Doctrinal Controversy* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2010).

¹⁷ Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Mango, 304; cf. Photius, *De Spiritu S. mystagogia*, ed. Hergenröther, 14, 15, 36, 37, 109.

¹⁸ Photius, “Liber de Spiritu Sancti Mystagogia”, in *Patrologiae Cursus Completus, Series Graeca*, ed. by Jean-Paul Migne, 102: 263-540 (Paris: Imprimerie Catholique, 1857-1866), 292B.

¹⁹ Stratoudaki White, *Patriarch Photios*, 74; Photius, *Epistolae*, Ed. Valetta, Ep. 5.

The main problems which emerge in Photius's and Pope Nicholas's correspondence are relevant to Photius's first mandate – and especially the Pope's accusations directed against Photius's formerly-held lay rank, as well as to the re-emergence of the *Filioque* dispute²⁰.

Upon the long dispute with the Greeks on doctrinal grounds, which additionally arose upon the occurrences in Bulgaria²¹, Pope Nicholas directs this exhaustive letter to Hicnmar in October 867 and exposes on the course of events²², as briefly mentioned above. The letter in question has been given the prime role in elucidation of the conflicts pertaining to the reign of Pope Nicholas and the enthronement of Photius; the *Annales Bertiniani* stress its importance²³.

Apart from the fertile field for intertwined missionary activities, directed from Francia, as well as Byzantium, Bulgaria also offers an excellent case-study for the relation between Christians and non-Christians, since it is on this area that the remains of paganism²⁴, and Paulicianism mingled. And also because it was the meeting point between missionaries from Rome and Constantinople, when the East and West come in touch.

Moreover, Photius aligns heresies to the semantic field of paganism and speaks of the “bacchantes and harpies of the heresies and schisms”, who are, as the children of heresy, “filled with corybantic frenzy” – thus comparing the heresies and heretics to the cultic phenomena of the pagan past: ...τὰ τέκνα σου, οὗς αἰρέσεων πάλαι καὶ σχισμάτων βάρχει καὶ ἄρπυιαι συναρπάσασαι καὶ πολλῆς κορυβαντίας ἐμπλήσασαι²⁵. Photius compares even the *Filioque* controversy, which achieved its peak at the time of the baptism of the Bulgars, to the field of

²⁰ Cf. Photius, *Epistolae*, ed. Migne, 593-617; Photius, “Epistolae”, in *Photii Patriarchae Constantinopolitani Epistulae et Amphiloquia*, vol. III, ed. Laourda, Ep. 288 (to Pope Nicholas), 114-120; Photius, Ep. 290 (to Pope Nicholas), in *Ibid.*, 123-138; Cf. Dvornik, *The Photian Schism*, 93-102.

²¹ Cf. Dvornik, *The Photian Schism*, 93-104.

²² Pope Nicholas. “Nicolai I papae Epistolae”, in *Monumenta Germaniae Historica*, Epistolae in Quart, 6, ed. by Ernst Perels (Berlin: Weidmann, 1925), 257-690, here Ep. 100, 601-609.

²³ Cf. *Ibid.*, note 2 on page 601, under the year 867, p. 89 sq.

²⁴ Cf. Tsvetelin Stepanov, “Periphery as Universe”, in *Byzantinoslavica* 59 (1998) fasc. 2: 247–254; Id., “From ‘steppe’ to Christian empire and back: Bulgaria between 800 and 1100”, in *The Other Europe in the Middle Ages: Avars, Bulgars, Khazars and Cumans*, ed. by Florin Curta (Leiden/Boston: Brill, 2007) 363-378; Id., *Религии в езическа България. Историографски подходи*. (София: Парадигма, 2017), 27-88, 170-194.

²⁵ Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Mango, 310; Φωτίου Ὁμιλίαι, ed. Β. Λαουρδα (“Homilies”, ed. by Vasileios Laourda, Thessaloniki, 1959), 176, l. 11-13.

Greek mythology²⁶: *δυσσεβῶν μύθοι*²⁷ ...οἱ τῶν Ἑλλήνων μύθοι²⁸ ...μέχρις ἂν εἰς τὴν ἑλληνικὴν πολυπληθίαν ἐκπέσωσι²⁹.

In one of his letters³⁰, which he elaborates on Arius and his heresy, Photius compares the heresy with Jewish and Greek manner of thinking: "...just as it is Jewish and Christ-hating to confound the majesty and monarch of the Trinity in one person, so it is Greek and polytheistic to divide the simple Godhead, which exceeds being and nature, into unequal and dissimilar beings": ...ὥσπερ τὸ εἰς ἓν συγκλείειν πρόσωπον τὴν Τριαδικὴν μοναρχίαν καὶ κυριότητα Ἰουδαϊκὸν ἐστὶ καὶ μισόχριστον, οὕτω καὶ τὸ κατατέμνειν εἰς ἀνίσους φύσεις καὶ ἀνομοίους οὐσίας τὴν ὑπερούσιον καὶ ὑπερφυῆ καὶ ἐνιαίαν Θεότητα Ἑλληνικὸν ὑπάρχει καὶ πολύθεον³¹. This comparison made by Photius clearly means that he finds the narrow strand dividing some of the pagan contemplation practices and procedures from the Christian heretical ones. So, in this letter, Photius undoubtedly compares the heresy of Arianism with Hellenic religion and polytheism, as well as with Jewish religion.

*Photius on the Russian attack – the siege of Constantinople of 860*³²

Photius consecrated two of his homilies on the attack and on the siege of Constantinople – undertaken by the Russians. Interestingly, these two homilies offer some glimpses and instructive material into how Photius observes a foreign enemy – who simultaneously is pagan – in comparison with how he addresses the enemy of Christianity - heresies and heretics.

²⁶ Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Mango, 304; cf. Photius, *De Spiritus S. mystagogia*, ed. Hergenröther, 14, 15, 36, 37, 109.

²⁷ Photius, *De Spiritus S. Mystagogia*, ed. Migne, 292A.

²⁸ Photius, *Encyclica Epistola*, ed. Migne, 728C.

²⁹ Photius, *Encyclica Epistola*, ed. Migne, 729C.

³⁰ Cf. Stratoudaki White, *Patriarch Photios*, 71.

³¹ Cf. Photius, *Epistolae*, ed. Valetta, Ep. 6, 206.

³² Cf. Pope Nicholas, *Epistolae*, 479-480 on the siege of Constantinople of 860. For more information on this event, see: Alexander Vassiliev, *The Russian Attack on Constantinople in 860* (Cambridge-MA: The Mediaeval Academy of America, 1925); Constantin Zuckerman, "Deux étapes de la formation de l'ancien état russe", in *Les centres proto-urbains russes entre Scandinavie, Byzance et Orient. Actes du Colloque International tenu au Collège de France en octobre 1997*, ed. by Michel Kazanski, Anne Nersessian and Constantin Zuckerman (Paris: P. Lethielleux, 2000), 95-120.

Photius refers to the Russians, coming from the sea to invade Constantinople, as “the hail-storm of barbarians”³³, or simply an inhuman barbarous tribe³⁴. He asks himself, did the inhabitants of Constantinople deserve it as a consequence of their sins³⁵. Curiously, but not completely unexpected, Photius refers to the Russians as to the incumbent plague – *ἡ παροῦσα θραῦσις* – employing the same collocation as in instances when he was referring to heretics³⁶. The same expression designating illness is used to describe the disaster provoked by the aggressors: the “plague of war” has spread out – *ἡ θραῦσις ἐξήπλωτο καὶ ὁ τοῦ πολέμου λοιμός*³⁷.

In this example, the recurrence to the terminology of the plague (disease), falls into the same semantic field as employed in describing heretics, and represents a *topos*³⁸.

Michael II to Louis the Pious on Thomas the Slav in 820's

In the account on Thomas the Slav, the idiom “*pagani et alienique*”³⁹ was used. Apparently, a connection or a semantic field between the heretics and pagans existed in the “textual set” of the Early Medieval authors.

Apparently both, Louis the Pious (814-833) and Michael II (820-829), aspired towards establishing and reinforcing contacts between Byzantium and Francia.

The rebellion of Thomas the Slav induced disorder in the Christian community. Namely, during the reign of Leo the Armenian (813-820), Thomas the Slav, referred to as the “disciple of the Devil”⁴⁰, was the commander of five themes of Asia Minor, and later promoted into the rank of the *turmarch* of the federates by Leo the Armenian⁴¹. Thomas the Slav apparently allied himself

³³ Photius, *Homilies*, 3rd Homily, ed. Mango, 82; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda, 29, l. 5.

³⁴ Photius, *Homilies*, 4th homily, ed. Mango, 96; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda, 40, l. 15-16.

³⁵ Photius, *Homilies*, 3rd homily, ed. Mango, 83; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda, 29, l. 12-13.

³⁶ Photius, *Homilies*, 3rd homily, ed. Mango, 85, 92; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda, 31, l. 27-28, 36, l. 24.

³⁷ Photius, *Homilies*, 4th homily, ed. Mango, 99; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda, 43, l. 10-11.

³⁸ For more information on the topoi in textual treatment of heresies in the Early Medieval period, see my forthcoming dissertation: *Language of Religious Dissent: A Comparative Perspective (9th-century Frankish and Byzantine Authors)*.

³⁹ Paul Lemerle, “Thomas le Slave”, in *Travaux et Mémoires I* (1965): 255-297, here 256-7.

⁴⁰ Michael, *Epistola*, 476, l. 8.

⁴¹ Lemerle, *Thomas le Slave*; Treadgold, Warren. *The Byzantine Revival 780-842*. Stanford: Stanford University Press, 1988), 196, 198.

with Paulicians and Iconophiles⁴². The account of Thomas's rebellion offers an example of combatting the common enemy who allied East and West in diplomatic purposes.

Michael II addressed the letter in question to Louis the Pious in 824, on his behalf and on behalf of his son Theophilus, who was made co-ruler in 821. This letter is preserved in Latin only⁴³. Michael sent gifts to Louis and to the Pope, which Louis's legates brought to Rome soon after⁴⁴. Michael alludes to Louis as to his *spiritalis frater* and *pacificus amicus*⁴⁵. The reason which led Michael to compose the letter, was ...*quia (Deus) permisit propter quaedam peccata subjecti populi sui provenire quasdam tribulationes*. The rebellion of Thomas the Slav, already ended by that time, reflected these troubles partially, which befell Byzantium. Furthermore, the Iconophile opposition to the measures undertaken by the emperor was fierce. Thomas appeared, writes Michael, in the times of his predecessor Leo V the Armenian – as a devil's apprentice and an executor of his work (...*diaboli discipulus, et eius operum promptus perpetrator*)⁴⁶. Thomas had renounced his Christian faith and thus betrayed it: *fidem Christi abnegans et hoc modo proditor fidei Christianae fuit*⁴⁷ – so that he could easier gather together the Saracens and other barbarians: ...*quo facilius potuisset multos infideles et Sarracenorum et ceterarum aliarum gentium ad suam perducere voluntatem*⁴⁸. In the turmoil which befell the Empire, Leo the Emperor got assassinated in a conjuration. The Christians found themselves divided. The chain of these turbulent events provoked, thus, the disunion and disintegration in the Christian flock: ...*invenimus Christianos divisos et discordantes*⁴⁹, whereas Thomas is referred to as *impius tyrannus*⁵⁰. Thomas's military units grew through time – encompassing forces from Thrace, Macedonia, Thessaloniki and Slavic bordering regions – and sieged Constantinople for

⁴² Stephanos Efthymiadis, "Notes on the Correspondence of Theodore the Studite", in *Revue des Études Byzantines* 53 (1995): 141-163, here 153; Treadgold, *Revival*, 234-244; on more information against the Iconophiles: Lemerle, *Thomas le Slave*, 260.

⁴³ On this letter, see also Einhard. "Annales, a. 741-829", in *Monumenta Germaniae Historica, Scriptores in Folio I, Annales et Chronica aevi Carolini*, ed. by Georg-Heinric Pertz (Hannover: Typis Culemannorum, 1826), 135-218, here an. 824, 212; cf. Тибор Живковић, *Јужни Словени под византијском влашћу 600-1025* (Београд: Чигоја, 2007?), 237-239.

⁴⁴ Emperor Michael II, "Michaelis et Theophili imperatorum Constantinopolitanorum epistola ad Hludowicum imperatorem directa" 824 m. Aprili, in *Monumenta Germaniae Historica, Concilia II, 2*, ed. by Albert Werminghoff (Hannover/Leipzig: Typis Culemannorum, 1908), 475-480, here 474; Cyril Mango, *The Art of the Byzantine Empire 312-1453: Sources and Documents*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press in association with the Medieval Academy of America, 1986), 157-158; on the historical context of the letter, see: Noble, *Images, Iconoclasm, and the Carolingians*, 260-263.

⁴⁵ Michael, *Epistola*, 478, l. 9, 13-14; Cf. Thomas Noble, *Images, Iconoclasm, and the Carolingians* (Philadelphia/PA: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2009).

⁴⁶ Michael, *Epistola*, 476, l. 8.

⁴⁷ Michael, *Epistola*, 476, l. 13

⁴⁸ Michael, *Epistola*, 476, l. 14-15.

⁴⁹ Michael, *Epistola*, 476, l. 38.

⁵⁰ Michael, *Epistola*, 476, l. 39.

a year⁵¹. Finally, the rebellion led by Thomas, the “devil and seducer of Christians”, and supported by his followers, pagans and strangers, *pagani et alienigenae*⁵² – got suppressed. From that time, the unity and concord spread again in the Christian Empire, by the merit of God, who united his people in faith: *...ex eo tempore omnes Christiani imperii nostri ad unitatem pacis et pristinam concordiam redierunt, glorificantes et magnificantes propugnatorem nostrum dominum Iesum Christum, qui ad unitatem fidei coadunare populum suum dignatus est*⁵³. With these words, Michael reinforced his relations with Louis the Pious, underlying the adherence to the one and the same faith binding the Eastern and Western empires together, and referring to both as guardians of *unius eiusdemque fidei et religionis*⁵⁴.

On more than one occasion, Michael underlines the connection with the West: he addresses Louis as *spiritali fratri nostro et pacifico amico*, and insists upon the reinforcement of their peaceful relation: *...par has nostras veras et fideles syllabas corroboramus et confirmamus priorem pacem et amicitiam inter vos et nos constitutam*⁵⁵.

In support of the true, genuine Christian faith which allies both Eastern and Western Empires, Michael alludes to its very foundations, testified and sealed by the six Ecumenical councils, Trinity and Christology: *...trinitatem in tribus personis divisam colimus, unitatem unius divinitatis naturam confitentis, divinitatis et humanitatis duas voluntates et operationes gloriamur*⁵⁶.

Speaking of the *seductores pseudochristiani, ecclesiae calumniatores*⁵⁷, if they appear, Michael underlines, they should be ejected: *Eicite malum de medio vestri* (Deut. 21:21) – and not only from the state, but also from the *ecclesia*, responsible for the spiritual well-being⁵⁸.

⁵¹ Michael, *Epistola*, 477, l. 2-12.

⁵² Michael, *Epistola*, 477, l. 21.

⁵³ Michael, *Epistola*, 478, l. 5-7.

⁵⁴ Michael, *Epistola*, 478, l. 11.

⁵⁵ Michael, *Epistola*, 478, l. 13-14; 27-28.

⁵⁶ Michael, *Epistola*, 479, l. 28-30.

⁵⁷ Michael, *Epistola*, 480, l. 1.

⁵⁸ Michael, *Epistola*, 480, l. 2-5.

Concluding remarks: outsiders and alieni

Concerned for the growth of the seed of *fides recta* among the newly-baptized Bulgars – as a counterbalance to idolatry⁵⁹, and hoping to prevent their potential return to paganism, the Pope advises them, and refers to St. Paul’s epistle⁶⁰ in reminding them that those who are “outside”, do not represent St. Paul’s concern: *Nam eos, qui foris sunt, Deus iudicabit...De his, qui extra religionem nostram sunt, nihil ego iudico, sed eos Dei iudicio reservo, qui iudicaturus est omnem carnem*⁶¹. Furthermore, the pagans and idolaters are expressly pinpointed as those who fall outside the society and official hierarchical grades – those who consider their sect more trustworthy and sacred than Christianity: *...per hoc veratiorem et sanctiorem suam sectam quam nostram existimet religionem*⁶². Additionally, the alliance with pagans is wishful only to the degree to which it pertains *ad cultum veri Dei*, since believers and non-believers do not have nothing in common⁶³; *Inveniuntur autem nonnulli sanctorum et fidelium cum alienigenis et infidelibus pacta et amicitiae foedere contraxisse diversa*⁶⁴. Returning to the afore-mentioned, these foreigners, or *alienigeni*, could be semantically related to those fallen outside of society – referred to as the severed limbs – and thus picturesquely portraying those as severed members of society⁶⁵.

The term *alienus* is similarly applied for Photius, who started his career firstly as a layman: in another letter, Pope Nicholas inserts in his condemnation of Photius’s election, the narrative of the lay and clerical ranks: having thus ascended from a lay rank, Photius reached the patriarchal office too swiftly: *...ac per hoc fit, ut alienus comedat ipsorum fructus laborum et stipendia meritorum extraneus hostis insperatus subripiat...*⁶⁶. With these words, the Pope implies the status of a foreigner to the laymen, in affairs pertaining to the ecclesiastical cursus.

After having exposed the relevant textual passages, the underlying semantic field of the “foreigner” should be emphasized as predominant in the afore-elaborated and analyzed narratives, whether on the pagans, or on the heretics. Moreover, the concept of “foreigner” (*alienus*) could be observed as the bearer of meaning, the key-word, the common denominator,

⁵⁹Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 99, 582, l. 40.

⁶⁰ Cf. 1 Cor. 5:12,13.

⁶¹ Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 99, 583, l. 20-22.

⁶²Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 99, 583, l. 24-25.

⁶³Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 99, 594, l. 38-41.

⁶⁴Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 99, 595, l. 2-3.

⁶⁵ Cf. Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 99, 576, l. 40-41.

⁶⁶ Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 98, 564, l. 8-11.

in theological positioning and self-representation in respect to other groups and/or individuals who were designed as “others”⁶⁷, thus pertaining to a much wider discursive sphere which would unambiguously encompass broader religious and chronological frame⁶⁸.

ABSTRACT:

Paganism was often considered by the Early Medieval Christian missionaries only as an erroneous approach/interpretation of Christian religion. The aim of this paper is to demonstrate, on the chosen case-studies, the textual treatment of heresy and paganism in the selected passages of 9th-century Greek and Latin authors, and in their texts which offer some insights on the Slavic populations. The topics discussed include: the accounts of Photius and Pope Nicholas I on the baptism of the Bulgarians; Photius’s narrative on the Russians and pagans, and the account of the rebellion of Thomas the Slav. After having conducted the analysis of the accounts of Photius, Pope Nicholas I and Michael II, and having submitted the relevant examples to the terminological scrutiny, the underlying semantic field of the “foreigner” can be emphasized as predominant in the given narratives, whether on pagans, or on the heretics. We may conclude that the concept of “alien”, “foreign” was the bearer of meaning, or the key-word, in theological positioning and self-representation in respect to other groups and/or individuals who were designed as “others”, pertaining to a much wider discourse, encompassing broader religious and chronological frame.

⁶⁷ Cf. Eduard Iricinschi and Holger M. Zellentin, “Making selves and marking others: identity and Late Antique heresiologies”, in *Introduction to Heresy and Identity in Late Antiquity*, ed. Id. (Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 2008) 1-27; Daniela Müller, “Our image of ‘Others’ and the own identity”, in *Iconoclasm and Iconoclasm. Struggle for Religious Identity. Jewish and Christian Perspectives Series 14*, ed. by Willem van Asselt et al. (Leiden/Boston: Brill, 2007) 107-125.

⁶⁸ Cf. for example, the gnostic concepts.

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